

Economic Feasibility Study of the OPL-70 Project in Field X at PT. BMM

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ABSTRACT: This study aims to evaluate the economic feasibility of the OPL-70 Project, which involves drilling 100 development wells in Field X within the East Borneo working area under the Production Sharing Contract (PSC) Cost Recovery framework. The study employs a quantitative approach using a Discounted Cash Flow (DCF) model covering the 2025–2033 evaluation period. Key economic indicators, including Net Present Value (NPV), Internal Rate of Return (IRR), Profitability Index (PI), and Discounted Payback Period, are applied to assess the project’s financial viability. Risk and uncertainty are addressed through sensitivity analysis and Monte Carlo simulation to capture the effects of variations in gas production, gas prices, and intangible capital expenditure. The results indicate that the OPL-70 Project generates a positive NPV of USD 18.53 million, an IRR of 13.56% exceeding the company’s hurdle rate, and a PI of 1.05, confirming its economic attractiveness. Probabilistic analysis shows a 96.92% probability of achieving a positive NPV, with limited downside risk. The study concludes that the OPL-70 Project is economically feasible and capable of enhancing gas recovery while extending the economic life of the mature field. The findings provide practical implications for investment decision-making and offer a structured reference for evaluating similar mature gas field developments.

KEYWORDS: Discounted Cash Flow; Economic Feasibility; Mature Gas Field; Monte Carlo Simulation; Production Sharing Contract.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the oil and gas industry, particularly in mature fields such as those operated by PT. BMM, efficient development planning plays a crucial role in well planning and decision making, especially in Field X. Due to the natural decline resulting from continuous production activities, additional wells are required to mitigate the sharpness of this decline (**Figure 1**).

Figure 1. Field X Gas Production
(Source: Internal Document of PT. BMM)

However, in the case of Field X, production activities have led to reservoir pressure depletion, which further complicates drilling operations. This condition requires more advanced drilling technologies, consequently increasing operation costs. In addition, surface preparation and rig costs further contribute to the overall economic challenges, making the drilling of new wells less economically feasible. Therefore, a more robust field development planning approach is needed to ensure that drilling activities can be carried out more efficiently and cost-effectively.

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As part of the continuous effort to sustain production and optimize existing assets in the East Borneo, the OPL (Operasi Pengembangan Lapangan) project has been initiated as one of the key field development programs. The project focuses on maximizing hydrocarbon recovery and extending the block's economic life through the drilling of additional development wells and integration with existing surface facilities. Implemented under the PSC Cost Recovery framework, the OPL-70 Project is designed to capture incremental value from remaining reserves, enhance production efficiency, and support Indonesia's national energy supply objectives while maintaining economic feasibility within the block's operational boundaries. A total of 100 wells are planned for drilling under the OPL-70 Project, with estimated gas reserves of 80.66 Bscf. The OPL-70 Project is scheduled to onstream in 2026, with an estimated investment value of USD 407.25 Million.

PT. BMM operating within the East Borneo working area. As one of the largest oil and gas blocks in Indonesia, East Borneo working area covers a 2,883.91 km² area with seven oil and gas producing sites. One of the largest fields in East Borneo working area is Field X. Field X is located in swamp area of East Borneo working area. The first well in this field was drilled in 1982 (Figure 2).

Figure 2. East Borneo Working Area
(Source: Internal Document of PT. BMM)

II. BUSINESS ISSUE AND RESEARCH QUESTION

The business issue is analysed using the 4W1H approach (What, When, Where, Why and How) to clearly define the operational challenge and the scope of the research. The business issue concerns the economic feasibility of the OPL-70 drilling campaign in the East Borneo working Area, which involves the drilling of 100 new wells to enhance gas recovery and extend field life. The challenge lies in balancing production targets with high operational costs driven by field maturity, complex well locations, and the use of advanced drilling technologies (What). The project's economic evaluation period spans from 2025 to December 31, 2033, aligning with the projected onstream schedule in 2026 and the estimated economic limit of the East Borneo working area based on long-term cash flow simulation (When). The project is located in Field X, within the East Borneo working area operated under the PSC Cost Recovery framework. As natural production from existing wells continues to decline, an extensive drilling program is required to sustain production levels and maximize recoverable reserves (Where). This initiative is also essential to optimize cost efficiency and improve economic returns for both PT. BMM and the Government of Indonesia (Why). The economic evaluation is conducted for the OPL-70 project, assessing cash flow and financial feasibility. This approach allows the analysis to capture the project's direct economic value to PT. BMM (How).

The research question to be analysed in this study is whether the drilling of 100 planned wells under the OPL-70 Project in Field X is economically feasible to be developed. This study aims to evaluate if the implementation of OPL-70 can effectively enhance gas recovery, increase hydrocarbon reserves, and generate added value for both PT. BMM and the Government of Indonesia within the current PSC Cost Recovery framework.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study applies a quantitative framework supported by qualitative context from internal field knowledge. This design aligns with the nature of the OPL-70 evaluation, which requires financial modelling to be grounded in actual operational conditions. This study progresses through several key stages, beginning with the formulation of the business issue and theoretical foundation, and continuing through data gathering, model development, economic assessment, and uncertainty evaluation.

This structured progression ensures that each analytical step builds on reliable information and reflects the logical flow of a feasibility study. A summary of the process is illustrated in the research design flowchart (Figure 3).

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Figure 3. Research Design

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter presents the results and discussion of the analyses conducted to evaluate the feasibility of the OPL-70 Project. Based on the combined economic assessment and external environment analysis, the results are interpreted to formulate a feasible business solution that balances value creation with operational constraints and risk exposure.

The external business environment of the OPL-70 Project is reviewed using the PESTEL analysis to understand external factors that may influence project feasibility within Indonesia’s upstream oil and gas sector. The project is operated by PT. BMM and is located in Field X, a mature gas field situated in a swamp environment within an established producing area. As a mature field development, the project is shaped by national energy policy, contractual obligations under the PSC Cost Recovery framework, and the need to sustain production over the remaining field life.

From a political perspective, the project operates within Indonesia’s established governance and regulatory framework for upstream oil and gas activities. Operations are governed by PSC arrangements, which provide clarity in fiscal terms while imposing obligations such as Domestic Market Obligation (DMO). Alignment with national energy supply priorities supports regulatory consistency; however, the project remains subject to potential policy adjustments related to fiscal terms, cost recovery mechanisms, and state revenue optimization. These aspects are therefore considered as part of the overall project risk.

The economic impact of the OPL-70 Project is primarily related to gas demand and prices. Gas revenues are supported by long term contractual arrangements with price assumptions derived from the Weighted Average Price (WAP). This pricing mechanism helps limit short term market exposure and provides stable revenues. The project also requires careful capital management due to the substantial upfront investment required for drilling, workover, and well intervention operations conducted in mature gas fields, which can potentially increase costs.

Social factors are relevant given the project’s location in an established producing area with long-standing interaction between upstream operations and surrounding communities. PT. BMM is expected to maintain appropriate excellent of health, safety, and community engagement, while supporting local employment and contractor participation. Mature field development activities also contribute to workforce continuity and local economic activity, which helps reduce non-technical operational risks.

In technological factor, the project relies on proven drilling, workover, and well intervention methods that are suitable for swamp operating environments. Field X is characterized by limited accessibility and logistical constraints, where drilling and Put-on-Production (POP) activities are commonly executed using barges rather than conventional rigs. As a result, execution efficiency, intervention scheduling, and well performance optimization become key technical considerations. The intensity of well intervention activities typical of mature swamp fields further increases the importance of operational planning and cost control.

Environmental considerations remain important, particularly due to the sensitivity of swamp areas. Operations in Field X are subject to environmental regulations related to emissions, waste management, and protection of surrounding ecosystems. While mature field developments generally involve lower incremental environmental impact compared to greenfield projects, strict compliance with environmental permits and operating standards is still required to manage environmental and reputational risks.

From a legal factor, the project operates within Indonesia’s oil and gas regulatory framework under PSC terms, which define cost recovery mechanisms, taxation, and contractual rights and obligations. Regulatory oversight provides a clear legal basis for investment decisions, although ongoing compliance with reporting, safety, and environmental requirements remains an integral part of project execution.

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Overall, the PESTEL analysis indicates that the external business environmental factors for the OPL-70 Project are manageable and support the project implementation.

A. Production Profile

Gas production begins in 2026 following the initial drilling program and increases as wells are completed and Put-on-Production (POP). However, production does not rise immediately during peak drilling activity due to the time lag between drilling completion and POP execution. Since POP activities rely on intervention barges and are subject to scheduling constraints, production growth continues after the peak drilling period. Gas production subsequently reaches a peak of 63.88 MMSCFD in 2029, once most wells are tied in, before gradually declining as the project enters the production sustainment phase (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Estimated Gas Production

B. Capital Expenditure (CAPEX) Analysis

The project requires a total investment of USD 407.25 million. Intangible CAPEX constitutes the largest portion of this investment, reflecting costs associated with drilling activities and subsurface operations, while tangible CAPEX is primarily related to drilling equipment and surface facilities. The concentration of capital expenditure during the peak drilling years shows a strong correlation with the number of wells drilled, indicating that CAPEX deployment is driven by operational intensity. The remaining intangible CAPEX in the years after 2030 mainly represents well intervention and workover activities required to sustain and optimize production in the mature field (Figure 5).

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	Total	2025	2026	2027	2028	2029	2030	2031	2032	2033
	(in Million USD)									
Total CAPEX	407.25	-	58.92	198.52	91.86	43.23	9.91	3.92	0.88	-
Tangible CAPEX	126.00	-	22.80	60.32	30.18	12.71	-	-	-	-
Drilling Tangible	46.35	-	8.18	25.01	10.37	2.79	-	-	-	-
Surface Tangible	79.65	-	14.62	35.31	19.81	9.92	-	-	-	-
Intangible CAPEX	281.25	-	36.13	138.21	61.67	30.52	9.91	3.92	0.88	-
Number of Well Drilled	100	0	18	47	26	9	0	0	0	0

Figure 5. Capital Expenditure (CAPEX)

C. Operating Expenditure (OPEX) Analysis

The total Operating Expenditure (OPEX) for the project is estimated at USD 27.14 million over the project life. OPEX commences in 2026 and increases in line with the ramp-up of field operations. Following drilling activities, newly drilled wells are not immediately Put-on-Production, as well commissioning and tie-in activities are carried out using intervention barges rather than drilling rigs and are therefore dependent on barge availability and scheduling. This operational constraint results in OPEX remaining elevated even as drilling activity begins to decline. In particular, the upward trend and peak in OPEX in 2029, despite a reduction in new well drilling activity, are primarily driven by the timing gap between the completion of drilled wells and their POP execution (Figure 6).

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	Total	2025	2026	2027	2028	2029	2030	2031	2032	2033
	(in Million USD)									
Total OPEX	27.14	-	0.65	3.45	6.54	8.16	5.59	2.29	0.46	-
Number of Well Drilled	100	0	18	47	26	9	0	0	0	0

Figure 6. Operating Expenditure (OPEX)

D. Oil and Natural Gas Price Assumption

PT. BMM periodically updates the oil and gas price forecasts as part of the long-term strategic planning process. The crude oil price assumption applied in this study is based on the Indonesian Crude Price (ICP) forecast, which is developed by considering key fundamental drivers, including macroeconomic conditions, global supply–demand dynamics, OECD inventory levels, and OPEC spare production capacity.

Natural gas price assumptions are represented by a Weighted Average Price (WAP), calculated from multiple gas sales contracts held by PT. BMM to capture variations in contract terms and customer profiles. The WAP is determined by weighting each contract price according to its respective gas delivery volume in each period, thereby providing a realistic representation of the blended gas price used in the economic evaluation (Figure 7).

	2025	2026	2027	2028	2029	2030	2031	2032	2033
	(ICP in USD/bbl)								
Oil Price Forecast	7.85	7.39	7.20	7.55	7.68	7.82	7.84	7.55	7.88
	(WAP in USD/MMBtu)								
Natural Gas Price Forecast	71.60	66.38	67.23	70.09	73.39	78.92	84.72	88.61	89.11

Figure 7. Oil and Natural Gas Price Forecast

E. Discount Rate (WACC / Hurdle Rate)

The WACC is applied as the discount rate in calculating the NPV of the project’s free cash flows. The WACC reflects the combined cost of debt and equity used to finance the investment. In this study, a capital structure of equity and debt is based on debt-to-equity ratio observed from PT. BMM financial statements for the year 2023 (Table 1).

Table 1. WACC Calculation

WACC Calculation		
Weight of Capital		
Equity Ratio over Capitalization	Strategic Plan	42.7%
Debt Ratio over Capitalization	Strategic Plan	57.3%
Total		100%

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COST OF EQUITY CALCULATION		
Levered Beta	Damodaran	0.88
Risk-Free Rate	IBPA 10 years Government Bond	7.0%
Risk Premium	Damodaran	6.87%
Cost of Equity	Calculated	13%
COST OF DEBT CALCULATION		
Cost of Debt Before Tax	Holding Bonds	5.63%
Tax	PSC Terms	36.25%
Cost of Debt After Tax	Calculated	4%
Cost of Debt	Calculated	4%
WACC Calculation		
Capital Asset Pricing Model		
WACC	Calculated	8.79%

Based on the calculation, the WACC obtained in this study is 8.79%, which is lower than the current company hurdle rate applied by PT. BMM of 10.22%. Since the company hurdle rate is higher than the calculated WACC therefore the company hurdle rate is used as the discount rate for this project investment analysis. The hurdle rate is used because it reflects more conservative evaluation approach, as it includes additional project specific risk, operational uncertainties, and strategic considerations that is not be captured in the calculated WACC.

F. Depreciation Schedule and Cost

Depreciation is calculated using a straight-line depreciation factor of 25% per year in accordance. Depreciation is charged annually at 25% of the original capital cost during the asset’s useful life. Any remaining unrecovered book value is fully depreciated in the final year, resulting in varying annual depreciation charges while ensuring complete cost recovery over the depreciation period (Table 2).

Table 2. Depreciation Schedule and Cost

	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 4	Year 5
Asset Book Value	75%	56%	42%	32%	0%
Depreciation	25%	19%	14%	11%	32%
Cumulative Depreciation	25%	44%	58%	68%	100%

G. Cash Flow Evaluation (Net Cash Flow Analysis)

Based on the assumptions for revenue and cost calculations, the financial projection for the OPL-70 Project is developed. The resulting undiscounted cash flow for PT BMM is illustrates negative net cash flows during the early investment and drilling phase, followed by positive net cash flows as production ramps up. The cumulative net cash flow curve reflects the gradual recovery of initial investments and provides an initial indication of the project’s cash flow dynamics over the project life. By the end of the project life in 2033, the cumulative cash flow is projected to reach USD 58.04 million (Figure 8).

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Figure 8. Net Cash Flow

H. Financial Feasibility Analysis

The financial feasibility of the OPL-70 Project is assessed using a Discounted Cash Flow (DCF) approach with a hurdle rate of 10.22% as the discount rate, reflecting the company’s minimum acceptable return for investment decisions. The discounted net cash flow profile for PT. BMM shows negative discounted cash flows during the early years due to upfront capital investment and drilling activities. As production ramps up, discounted net cash flows turn positive, and the cumulative discounted cash flow gradually recovers the initial investment toward the later stage of the project life (Figure 9).

Figure 9. Discounted Net Cash Flow

The financial indicators derived from the DCF analysis are summarized in Table 3. The analysis results in a positive Net Present Value (NPV) of USD 18.53 million, indicating that the project creates value when evaluated against the hurdle rate. The Internal Rate of Return (IRR) is calculated at 13.56%, which exceeds the hurdle rate of 10.22%, confirming the project’s financial attractiveness. In addition, a Profitability Index (PI) of 1.05 further supports the economic feasibility of the project, as the present value of cash inflows exceeds the initial investment. The discounted payback period is estimated at approximately 6.2 years, reflecting the time required to recover the investment on a discounted basis. Overall, these results indicate that the OPL-70 Project is financially feasible under the base-case assumptions.

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Table 3. DCF result

NPV (in Million USD)	18.53
IRR	13.56%
Profitability Index	1.05
Discounted Payback Period (Years)	6.2

I. Sensitivity Analysis

Sensitivity analysis is conducted to evaluate the impact of variations in key economic and cost parameters on the Net Present Value (NPV) of the OPL-70 Project. In this analysis, all major parameters illustrated in the sensitivity chart: Gas Price, Gas Production, Intangible CAPEX, Tangible CAPEX (Drilling and Surface facilities), and OPEX are varied within a range of $\pm 30\%$ from their respective base-case values, while other variables are held constant. This wider range is applied to assess the relative influence of each parameter on project value (Figure 10).

Figure 10. Sensitivity Analysis

From the cost perspective, intangible CAPEX exhibits a more pronounced influence on NPV compared to drilling tangible CAPEX, surface tangible CAPEX, and OPEX. Increases in intangible CAPEX within the $\pm 30\%$ range lead to a substantial reduction in NPV and push the project value closer to the breakeven threshold, highlighting the importance of cost control in drilling and subsurface-related expenditures. Based on the sensitivity results, the breakeven condition is approached when intangible CAPEX increases toward the upper bound of the $\pm 30\%$ variation range. Drilling tangible CAPEX and surface tangible CAPEX show a moderate impact on NPV, while variations in OPEX result in relatively smaller changes in project value. This indicates that, although operating costs contribute to overall project economics, they are not the primary drivers of financial risk when compared to capital investment and production-related parameters.

Overall, the sensitivity analysis demonstrates that the economic viability of the OPL-70 Project is most strongly influenced by gas production, gas price, and intangible CAPEX. These findings provide a comprehensive understanding of the project’s risk profile and form the basis for selecting the most critical parameters for further uncertainty assessment using Monte Carlo simulation in the subsequent analysis.

J. Monte Carlo Simulation for Risk Assessment

Monte Carlo simulation were conducted using 5,000 iterations to analyze the combined uncertainty of the main parameters influencing the OPL-70 Project. The three parameters identified from the sensitivity analysis is gas production, gas price, and intangible CAPEX. For the Monte Carlo simulation, the minimum, base, and maximum cases was defined based on the company historical record from the similar project which was done previously by PT. BMM (Table 4).

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Table 4. Parameter for Monte Carlo Simulation

Parameters	Maximum	Base	Minimum
Gas Production	118%	100%	71%
Gas Price	119%	100%	79%
Intangible CAPEX	81%	100%	129%

The simulation results indicate that the project’s Net Present Value (NPV) remains predominantly positive across the simulated scenarios. The NPV outcomes range from a minimum of -12.00 million USD to a maximum of 36.12 million USD, demonstrating that although downside scenarios exist, the project also exhibits meaningful upside potential. The mean NPV of 13.11 million USD remains well above zero, confirming that the project generates economic value on average under uncertainty. The standard deviation of 6.94 million USD indicates a moderate level of variability around the mean, suggesting that fluctuations in project value are present but remain within a manageable range. Downside exposure is limited, with a probability of negative NPV of 3.08%, while the probability of achieving a positive NPV reaches 96.92% (**Table 5** and **Figure 11**).

When compared with the deterministic base-case NPV of 18.53 million USD, approximately 77.82% of simulated outcomes fall below the base-case value, indicating that the base case represents an optimistic yet still plausible scenario. Percentile analysis further clarifies the project’s risk profile. The P10 NPV of 4.31 million USD represents a conservative downside case, showing that even under unfavourable conditions the project generally remains economically viable. The P50 (median) NPV of 13.22 million USD reflects the most likely outcome when uncertainty across key parameters is considered and provides a more conservative benchmark than the deterministic base case. Meanwhile, the P90 NPV of 21.09 million USD highlights the project’s upside potential, indicating that favourable combinations of gas production performance and cost efficiency can generate economic returns exceeding the median outcome (**Table 5** and **Figure 11**).

Overall, the Monte Carlo simulation confirms that the OPL-70 Project exhibits a balanced risk profile, with limited downside risk, a positive central outcome, and shows upside potential, thereby reinforcing the project’s financial feasibility under a wide range of uncertainty scenarios.

Table 5. Monte Carlo Simulation result

NPV (in million USD)	
NPV Base	18.53
Minimum	(12.00)
Maximum	36.12
Mean	13.11
Standard Deviation	6.94
Median	13.22
Probability NPV < 0	3.08%
Probability NPV > 0	96.92%
Probability NPV < NPV Base	77.82%
P10	4.31
P50 (Median)	13.22
P90	21.99

Figure 11. NPV Probability Distribution by Monte Carlo Simulation

Based on the economic evaluation and risk analysis, the recommendation for OPL-70 Project is to proceed with the development under the base-case configuration while applying a conservative and disciplined execution strategy. The deterministic financial results confirm that the project is economically viable, with a positive Net Present Value (NPV) of USD 18.53 million, an Internal Rate of Return (IRR) of 13.56% that exceeds the company’s hurdle rate of 10.22%, and a Profitability Index (PI) of 1.05. In addition, the discounted payback period of approximately 6.2 years indicates that the initial investment can be recovered within a reasonable timeframe relative to the project life. These indicators demonstrate that the project meets the company’s investment criteria.

This conclusion is further strengthened by the risk analysis results. Sensitivity analysis identifies gas production and gas price as the primary value drivers, while intangible CAPEX represents the most critical cost-related risk. Monte Carlo simulation results show a high likelihood of economic success, with a probability of positive NPV of 96.92% and a relatively low probability of negative NPV of 3.08%. The probabilistic outcomes indicate that the project remains resilient under uncertainty. Accordingly, the proposed business solution emphasizes value preservation and risk management rather than aggressive upside pursuit, focusing on drilling efficiency, strict control of subsurface-related expenditures, and realistic scheduling that accounts for the delay between drilling completion and Put-on-Production (POP) due to intervention barge availability.

Based on financial feasibility, the OPL-70 is economically attractive under current assumptions that planned on stream in 2026 with the duration of project until December 2033 in the Field X of the East Borneo working area that is operated by PT. BMM. The implementation plan will be conducted in planning schedule as show in **Table 6** below.

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Table 6. OPL-70 Project Implementation Timeline

OPL-70 Project	2025				2026				2027				2028 - 2029			
	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4
PT. BMM																
Project Screening and Selection Phase																
Detailed Evaluation and Feasibility Assessment Phase																
Final Investment Decision (FID)																
SKK Migas																
POD Process																
POD Submission and Approval																
Permitting and Regulatory																
Environmental and Regulatory Permitting Phase																
Execution																
Survey and Site Preparation																
Drilling																
Well Connection																
Workover																
First Production																

V. CONCLUSIONS

This study aims to answer the research question of whether the drilling of 100 wells planned in the OPL-70 Project in Field X is economically feasible and can generate added value for PT. BMM. Based on the results discussed in Chapter IV, the OPL-70 Project is economically attractive based on the assumptions applied in this study and able to generate positive economic value during the project period.

The economic evaluation indicates that the OPL-70 project can increase gas production and reserves in Field X. The projected cash flow performance shows the resulting revenue is sufficient to recover the investment of the project. The project is economically feasible under various conditions and is most sensitive to changes in gas prices, gas production, and intangible CAPEX based on Sensitivity analysis and Monte Carlo simulation.

The external environmental assessment conducted using PESTEL analysis gives the insight that the feasibility of the OPL-70 Project is also influenced by non-economic factors. Political and legal considerations emphasize the importance of regulatory compliance and timely permitting, while economic factors highlight exposure to market volatility. Social, environmental, and technological factors indicate that the project could be implemented using more advanced technologies. These external factors do not negate the project's economic potential, but represent conditions that must be managed to ensure the successful implementation of the OPL-70 Project.

In conclusion, this study shows that drilling the 100 wells planned in the OPL-70 Project is economically feasible and capable of increasing gas production, increasing gas reserves, and generating added value in the Field X for the contractor and the Government of Indonesia.

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